

Project Handbook

Deliverable report

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Abbreviations

AI/ML	Artificial intelligence/machine learning
CA	Consortium agreement
CRISPR-Cas9	Clustered regularly interspaced palindromic repeats
CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas
EB	Executive board
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU-OS	EU-OPENSSCREEN
FFUL	Faculdade de Farmacia da Universidade de Lisboa
GA	Grant agreement
GA	General assembly
IBB PAN	Instytut Biochemii i Biofizyki Polskiej Akademii Nauk
ILO	Industry liaison office

IMG	Ustav Molekularni Genetiky Akademie ved Ceske Republiky Verejna Vyzkumna Institute
IPRs	Intellectual property rights
KI	Karolinska Institutet
MEDINA	Fundacion Centro de Excelencia en Investigacion de Medicamentos Innovadores en Andalucia
MoA	Mechanism of action
PMT	Project management team
PU	Public
RI	Research infrastructure
RNAi	Ribonucleic acid interference
RP	Reporting period
SAB	Scientific advisory board
UC	Universidade De Coimbra
UiO	University of Oslo
USC	University of Santiago de Compostela
WP	Work-package
WPLG	Work-package leaders group

1 Executive summary

The EU-OPENSSCREEN Research Infrastructure (EU-OS RI), a leading European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) for chemical biology and early drug discovery, offers services in high-throughput compound screening and medicinal chemistry to both academic and industrial users. As such, EU-OS RI is pivotal in advancing early-stage drug discovery in Europe. To meet the growing complexity of modern drug discovery research, EU-OS RI has recently expanded its services to include fragment-based drug discovery and chemoproteomics. The IMPULSE project will further enhance EU-OS RI by developing and integrating new services in AI/ML, novel chemical modalities and cutting-edge cell models combined with CRISPR-Cas9/RNAi-based genetic screening. Additionally, IMPULSE will implement standardised operational and data practices to improve reproducibility and data quality, while tailored outreach and training programmes will increase both awareness of the EU-OS RI's activities and the operational excellence of EU-OS RI. These efforts, along with new partnerships with industry and charities, will ensure the long-term sustainability and accessibility of EU-OS RI's comprehensive service portfolio.

This document represents a project handbook for the IMPULSE project, outlining the management and quality processes needed to enhance the infrastructure's capabilities and ensure its long-term sustainability.

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose of handbook

The IMPULSE Project Handbook is designed to help project partners manage and execute daily activities by offering clear guidelines, rules and processes. It outlines the overall management approach and provides practical tools, such as mailing lists, repositories and templates, to facilitate collaboration and ensure consistent communication among consortium members. It includes the following aspects:

- A summary of legal, administrative and financial obligations
- Roles and responsibilities for management, consortium and governance
- Internal procedures for communication, document management and template usage
- A quality assurance plan

The project handbook will serve as a key reference throughout the project's lifetime and will be updated as needed.

2.2 Core Information

General Aspects

The key information from the IMPULSE grant agreement data sheet includes:

Project number: 101132028

Project name: IMProving User experience, Long-term sustainability and Services of EU-OPENSREEN

Project acronym: IMPULSE

Call: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01

Topic: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-03

Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

Granting authority: European Research Executive Agency

Project starting date: 1 March 2024

Project end date: 28 February 2027

Project duration: 36 months

Consortium

The project handbook is shared among all consortium partners. The consortium brings together cutting-edge expertise and resources to strengthen the sustainability of the EU-OPENSREEN Research Infrastructure (EU-OS RI). This is achieved by diversifying funding sources, expanding EU-OS RI membership, growing the user community, enhancing and improving service offerings, optimising existing resources and forming partnerships with other RIs and stakeholders. IMPULSE unites 24 EU-OS RI partner sites across Europe, all leaders in chemical biology, who contribute their diverse experience and skills to the development of EU-OS RI. The IMPULSE consortium includes 10 countries: Germany, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, Latvia, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain and Sweden.

The list of IMPULSE partners is included in the Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement and presented here below:

Table 1 IMPULSE partners

Participants	Participant organisation name	Country
1	EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC (EU-OS), coordinator	DE
2	FORSCHUNGSVERBUND BERLIN EV (FVB-FMP)	DE
3	USTAV MOLEKULARNI GENETIKY AKADEMIE VED CESKE REPUBLIKY VEREJNA VYZKUMNA INSTITUCE (IMG)	CZ
4	UNIVERZITA PALACKEHO V OLOMOUCI (UP-IMTM)	CZ
5	MASARYKOVA UNIVERZITA (MU)	CZ
6	TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF DENMARK (DTU)	DK
7	FUNDACION CENTRO DE EXCELENCIA EN INVESTIGACION DE MEDICAMENTOS INNOVADORES EN ANDALUCIA (MEDINA)	ES
8	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS (CSIC)	ES
9	FUNDACION DE LA COMUNIDAD VALENCIANA CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION PRINCIPE FELIPE (CIPF)	ES
10	UNIVERSIDAD DE SANTIAGO DE COMPOSTELA SANTIAGO DE COMPOSTELA (USC)	ES
11	HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO (UH)	FI
12	INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACAO E INOVACAO EM SAUDE DA UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO (I3S)	PT
13	FACULDADE DE FARMÁCIA DA UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA (FFUL)	PT
14	KAROLINSKA INSTITUTET (KI)	SE
15	TURUN YLIOPISTO (UTU)	FI
16	LATVIJAS ORGANISKAS SINTEZES INSTITUTS (LIOS)	LV
17	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO (UiO)	NO
18	INSTYTUT BIOCHEMII I BIOFIZYKI POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK (IBB PAN)	PL
19	INSTYTUT BIOLOGII MEDYCZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK (IBM PAN)	PL
20	INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK (ICHB PAN)	PL
21	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA (UC)	PT
22	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV (Fraunhofer)	DE
23	UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO (U.PORTO)	PT
24	UNIVERSITETET I BERGEN (UiB)	NO

25	HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUR INFEKTIONSFORSCHUNG GMBH (HZI)	DE
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Work Packages

The project handbook is used across all IMPULSE work-packages (WPs).

IMPULSE's primary goal is to support the growth and long-term sustainability of the EU-OS RI by tackling four key themes:

- Theme 1: Expansion of EU-OS RI's catalogue of services and capabilities.
- Theme 2: Increasing the quality of the services and scientific output.
- Theme 3: Attracting new user communities.
- Theme 4: Ensuring long-term financial sustainability.

Under these themes, IMPULSE is organised into 11 complementary WPs, each focussing on a specific aspect of the project.

Table 2 IMPULSE WPs

WP	Title & short description
1	<p>Long-term sustainability and access procedures:</p> <p>WP1 will ensure EU-OS RI's sustainability by i) integrating novel services from WP3–6 and establishing access rules, workflows and procedures for these services and ii) expanding its global reach.</p>
2	<p>Creating a repository of community compounds:</p> <p>WP2 aims to incorporate unique novel compounds sourced from the chemistry community, subjecting them to thorough bio-profiling including cell painting.</p>
3	<p>Validating pharmacology using advanced disease models and genetic screens:</p> <p>WP3 aims to develop capabilities and workflows for validating hit bioactive compounds identified from large-screening campaigns using cellular models that accurately represent disease phenotypes. This approach will include analysing the compounds' mechanisms of action (MoA) through complementary genetic screening techniques.</p>

4	<p>New chemical modalities:</p> <p>WP4 aims to develop specialised services for new chemical modalities beyond traditional small molecules which are designed to target challenging targets (e.g., new chemical probes, targeted degraders, enzymatic modulators, multitarget molecules associated to polypharmacology).</p>
5	<p>Data reproducibility and operational standards:</p> <p>WP5 will focus on implementing common operational standards and increasing the quality and reproducibility of EU-OS RI's data.</p>
6	<p>ML/AI for identification of modes of action with cell painting and small molecule data:</p> <p>WP6 focusses on collecting and preprocessing data to apply deep learning techniques for predicting pathways and drug targets.</p>
7	<p>Training and capacity building:</p> <p>WP7 will enhance training activities, identify and address training needs, and develop training programmes for emerging areas in drug discovery covered in WP3–6.</p>
8	<p>Engagement with public–private initiatives:</p> <p>WP8 aims to identify and map the expertise and capabilities of the consortium's partner sites and disseminate this information to maintain ongoing engagement with industry.</p>
9	<p>Outreach and dissemination:</p> <p>WP9 will effectively communicate the EU-OPENSREEN and IMPULSE's objectives, findings, and impact to diverse stakeholders, including the public, user community, and industry, ensuring broad awareness and engagement.</p>

10	<p>Project management:</p> <p>WP10 works closely with all WPs to ensure smooth and coordinated project operation.</p>
11	<p>Ethics requirements:</p> <p>WP11 sets out the ethics requirements that the project must comply with according to the IMPULSE Grant Agreement.</p>

Budget

Maximum grant amount, total estimated eligible costs and contributions and funding rate are available in the Grant Agreement. The funding rate for costs is 80% of the action's eligible costs.

For more specific details on the grant, please refer to Article 5, pages 16–17 of the IMPULSE Grant Agreement (Appendix 1). Maximum grant amount, total estimated eligible costs and contributions and funding rate are displayed in the data sheet of the IMPULSE Grant Agreement at page 10.

2.3 Project roles and responsibilities

In IMPULSE, every partner and their team ensure that the project runs smoothly. By signing the Consortium Agreement (CA) and Grant Agreement (GA), partners agree to work together and fulfill all their responsibilities.

Partners need to keep their responsible WP leader(s) updated on the progress of their tasks.

Any major issues, delays or problems that arise that could affect the project must be reported immediately to the project coordinator (see below, IMPULSE Coordination). The coordinator will then inform the Grant Authority and the other partners.

IMPULSE Consortium Agreement (CA) and Grant Agreement (GA) are stored in the IMPULSE SharePoint under 'Legal Documents' (Appendix 1) and accessible to all consortium partners.

IMPULSE Coordination

IMPULSE is coordinated by EU-OPENSREEN ERIC.¹ The IMPULSE coordinator serves as the main link between the consortium partners and the Granting Authority.

The primary coordinator contact for the project is **Bahne Stechmann**, the Deputy Director of EU-OPENSREEN ERIC. He is also the chair of the General Assembly (GA) and the Executive Board (EB). The coordinator is responsible for submitting requests, reports and notifications to the Commission on behalf of the consortium.

¹ <https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/>

Therefore, EU-OS coordinates the project (WP10, management) and oversees all the work packages.

Supporting the coordinator is the Project Management Team (PMT), which includes:

- **Tanja Miletic**: IMPULSE Project Manager and lead for Work Package 10 (management); main contact.
- **Alexandra Ertman**: Science Communication Officer and lead for Work Packages 7 (training) and 9 (communication), supporting Work Package 10 (management).
- **Yasemin Ucal**: Scientific Project Manager, supporting Work Packages 1 (sustainability), 3 and 4 (scientific services).
- **Robert Harmel**: Scientific Project Manager, co-lead for Work Package 8 (industry).
- **Victoria Mora**: Compound Submission Manager, co-lead for Work Package 2 (academic compounds repository).

The PMT helps the GA, EB, Coordinator and Work Package Leaders Group with the daily management of the project and ensures its successful delivery.

For coordination, you can contact the team at IMPULSE-coordination@eu-openscreen.eu.

For more specific details on operational procedures for the Coordinator, please refer to Article 6.4, page 18 of the IMPULSE Consortium Agreement (Appendix 1).

Governance structure

The IMPULSE workplan spans three years and aims to improve and sustain the capabilities and services of EU-OS RI. Its governance structure is depicted in Figure 1.

IMPULSE's governance structure includes two boards: the **Executive Board** (EB) and the **General Assembly** (GA).

The contact details for GA, EB and WP leaders are available on the IMPULSE SharePoint under 'WP' > 'WP10_Management' > 'IMPULSE_Governance_registry' (Appendix 1).

This list is curated by the IMPULSE PMT. To be added to or removed from the list, email IMPULSE-coordination@eu-openscreen.eu.

Additionally, IMPULSE will have an external **Scientific Advisory Board** (SAB) of experts who will give strategic advice to enhance the impact of EU-OPENSSCREEN and IMPULSE. The **Industry Liaison Office** (ILO) in WP8 will help connect with industrial partners and organise industry-focussed workshops.

Figure 1 IMPULSE governance structure.

For more specific details on operational procedures for the governance structure please refer to pages 10–17 of the IMPULSE Consortium Agreement (Appendix 1).

Boards

General Assembly

The General Assembly (GA) is the main decision-making group for the IMPULSE consortium. It includes one representative from each project partner. The list of GA representatives and their deputies is available on the IMPULSE SharePoint (Appendix 1).

The GA operates as follows:

- The coordinator chairs the meetings.
- Each partner has one member and one vote (they may appoint deputies if needed).
- The GA meets at least once a year (see Table 5).
- A meeting requires at least two-thirds of the members to be present to make decisions.
- The GA creates proposals and makes decisions pertaining to the IMPULSE consortium / decisions related to the execution of the IMPULSE workplan.

For more specific details on operational procedures for the General Assembly, please refer to pages 15, 16 of the IMPULSE Consortium Agreement (Appendix 1).

Executive Board

The Executive Board (EB) oversees the execution of the project and reports to the GA.

The EB operates as follows:

- The coordinator leads the EB.
- The EB meets at least every three months (see Table 5).
- To make decisions, at least two-thirds of the members must be present.
- The EB proposes ideas for the GA to review.
- The EB carries out and implements the GA's decisions.

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- The EB gathers information on the project's progress.

The EB also helps the coordinator with meetings involving the Granting Authority and prepares related data and reports. It handles the timing and content of press releases and joint publications, following the procedures outlined in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

EB members were nominated by IMPULSE consortium partners in April 2024 and then elected by the GA. The current EB members are:

- **Bahne Stechmann** (coordinator), EU-OS
- **Tanja Miletic** (coordinator contact), EU-OS
- **Anna-Lena Gustavsson**, KI
- **Miguel Mano**, UC
- **Rui Moreira**, FFUL
- **Olga Genilloud**, MEDINA
- **Piotr Zielenkiewicz**, IBB PAN

For more specific details on operational procedures for the Executive Board, please refer to pages 16, 17 of the IMPULSE Consortium Agreement (Appendix 1).

Work Package Leaders Group

The Work Package Leaders Group (WPLG) includes the leads and co-leads of each WP (see Table 3 and board registry on SharePoint).

The WPLG monitors the progress of the work packages, makes sure related tasks are working together and checks that the project is running smoothly. It also reviews any suggestions from WP leads about changing/reallocating tasks or budgets.

The WPLG proposes amendments to the Grant Agreement and helps the coordinator and PMT with preparing for meetings by providing necessary data and deliverables. WP leaders are responsible for the communication with WP partners, and they ensure the proper implementation of tasks.

In IMPULSE the WPLG will meet monthly (see Table 5).

Table 3 List of IMPULSE WP leads and co-leads

WP	WP lead	WP co-lead
WP1(sustainability)	Bahne Stechmann (EU-OS)	
WP2 (academic compounds)	Mabel Loza (USC)	Victoria Mora (EU-OS)
WP3 (complex disease models)	Brinton Seashore-Ludlow (KI) <i>Proxy: Anna-Lena Gustavsson (KI)</i>	Miguel Mano (UC)
WP4 (new chemical modalities)	Ana Martinez (CSIC) <i>Proxy: Carmen Gil (CSIC)</i>	
WP5 (standardization)	Petr Bartůněk (IMG)	
WP6 (AI/ML)	Tiago Rodrigues (FFUL)	
WP7 (training)	Alexandra Ertman (EU-OS) <i>Proxy: Tanja Miletic (EU-OS)</i>	
WP8 (industry)	Mabel Loza (USC) <i>Proxy: Johannes Landskron (UiO)</i>	Robert Harmel (EU-OS)
WP9 (communication)	Alexandra Ertman (EU-OS) <i>Proxy: Tanja Miletic (EU-OS)</i>	

WP10 (management)	Tanja Miletic (EU-OS) Proxy: Alexandra Ertman (EU-OS)	
WP11 (ethics)	Tanja Miletic (EU-OS) Proxy: Yasemin Ucal (EU-OS)	

2.4 Internal communication

This section of the handbook provides guidelines on how to use key communication tools and resources.

Emails

Email is the primary tool for day-to-day communication in IMPULSE. It is used for formal correspondence and important updates. Mailing lists have been created by topic and are curated and managed by IMPULSE Coordination (see Table 4).

Requests to be added to/removed from a mailing list may be forwarded to IMPULSE-coordination@eu-openscreen.eu

Table 4 IMPULSE email lists

Email List group	Email	Description
IMPULSE-all	IMPULSE-all@eu-openscreen.eu	All project contacts
IMPULSE-admin	IMPULSE-admin@eu-openscreen.eu	Administrative contacts at each partner institution
IMPULSE-finance	IMPULSE-finance@eu-openscreen.eu	Finance contacts at each partner institution
IMPULSE-GA	IMPULSE_GA@eu-openscreen.eu	General assembly members
IMPULSE-EB	IMPULSE_EB@eu-openscreen.eu	Executive board members
IMPULSE-WPLG	IMPULSE_WPLG@eu-openscreen.eu	WP leaders and co-leaders
IMPULSE-WP1–10	IMPULSE-WP1@eu-openscreen.eu IMPULSE-WP2@eu-openscreen.eu IMPULSE-WP3@eu-openscreen.eu IMPULSE-WP4@eu-openscreen.eu IMPULSE-WP5@eu-openscreen.eu IMPULSE-WP6@eu-openscreen.eu IMPULSE-WP7@eu-openscreen.eu IMPULSE-WP8@eu-openscreen.eu IMPULSE-WP9@eu-openscreen.eu IMPULSE-WP10@eu-openscreen.eu	Participants in individual work packages. One email list per work package.

SharePoint & calendar

Microsoft SharePoint is used as a space to collaborate on and store project-internal documents. IMPULSE Coordination is responsible for monitoring, maintaining and granting access to SharePoint. All project partners may create and modify SharePoint documents as needed.

The IMPULSE SharePoint² also hosts a calendar, where the details for online, hybrid and in-person meetings pertaining to the consortium (e.g., WPLG meetings, annual in-person meetings, etc.) may be posted. Project partners who would like to make their meeting details available to the consortium may forward the event details to IMPULSE Coordination, who will then post them in the calendar.

² <https://euopenscreeneu.sharepoint.com/sites/EU-OPENSREEN-IMPULSE>

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If a partner is unable to access SharePoint, they are expected to communicate with IMPULSE Coordination to resolve any technical issues.

SharePoint access and assistance requests may be forwarded to SharePoint@eu-openscreen.eu. Partners may register for the IMPULSE SharePoint and mailing lists in a dedicated Microsoft form.³

Meetings

To ensure sufficient cross-consortium communication and advancement of the workplan, the IMPULSE project will be structured around several regular meetings among subgroups of partners (Table 5). Meetings dates are displayed in the SharePoint calendar. Virtual meetings organised by the coordinator will use Zoom as the conference tool.

Table 5 Descriptions of and organisational guidelines for all regular IMPULSE meetings.

Meeting Name	Details	When/ where
General Assembly meetings	In-person meeting with representatives of the GA, which is held once a year, with at least 45 days' notice. The coordinator will organise and lead this meeting. The agenda will be sent out 21 days before the meeting.	Once per year In-person
Executive Board meetings	A virtual or in-person meeting with the IMPULSE EB takes place every 3 months, with at least 14 days' notice. The coordinator will organise and lead the meeting, and the agenda will be sent out 7 days before. EB members are invited to propose topics for discussion.	Every 3 months Online
Work-package Leader Group meeting	A virtual or in-person meeting with the WPLG is held every month, with at least 14 days' notice. The coordinator will organise and lead the meeting, and the agenda will be sent out 7 days before. WP leads and co-leads are expected to prepare a flash report according to a set template to update the coordinator on WP progress, completed actions, deviations and risks. WP leads unable to attend a WPLG meeting must send a proxy to present on their behalf.	Every month Online
Work-package-specific meetings	Virtual or in-person meetings for specific WPs are scheduled regularly according to the workplan and as requested by the WP leaders (WPLs). Each WP-specific meeting will be organised and led by the WPL. Meeting dates must be shared with the IMPULSE PMT at least 10 days in advance.	Ad-hoc Online
Internal project management meetings	Internal PMT regular meetings will occur weekly. Meeting will be held virtually or in-person. Asana is used to track these meetings.	Every Tuesday Online/ in-person
Communication/ outreach meeting	The IMPULSE WP9 communication working group includes communication or outreach officers from each consortium partner. Virtual calls will be scheduled with the IMPULSE WP9 working group to coordinate outreach and dissemination activities. These meetings will occur every two months or as needed. Meeting	Every two months or as needed Online

³ Registration form for IMPULSE SharePoint and mailing lists:

https://forms.office.com/Pages/DesignPageV2.aspx?subpage=design&FormId=u0a62-a4V0iO2_pfc4Dpmdr2P5GVoGpHsaxEgg-0GSZUNEMzQzYzNzM0QVdCMExNUU1aNFhSTkhJMy4u&Token=133b9f3372ed46ca9a4336530c0cdf65

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	dates will be shared at least seven days in advance, and the agenda will be provided at least one day before the meeting.	
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Figure 2 SharePoint Meeting folder structure.

All meetings will be documented using the meeting minutes template available on SharePoint under the 'Template' folder (Appendix 1). Minutes of all meetings will be stored in the appropriate subfolder under the 'Meetings' folder (Figure 2) and shared with consortium members.

2.5 External communication

This section outlines main tools and protocols for sharing project updates, results and information with external audiences. By following these guidelines, we aim to enhance visibility, foster positive relationships and ensure clear and professional communication with all external parties.

Public engagement, key messages and target audiences will be detailed in the IMPULSE communication and dissemination plan.

EU acknowledgement & logo

All IMPULSE documentation and communication materials must acknowledge the European Union with the following statement:

Funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement No. 101132028. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Documentation and communication materials should also display the European Union flag alongside the statement 'Co-funded by the European Union'.⁴

Publication acknowledgement

All IMPULSE publications must include the following acknowledgement text:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101132028, project IMPULSE.

Branding guidelines & outreach materials

A set of IMPULSE branding guidelines (with details on visual identity, logos, typography and templates) is available on SharePoint (Appendix 1). All partners should refer to these guidelines when creating material for project communication to external audiences.

Several document templates and boilerplate texts have been or will be deposited on SharePoint in the 'Outreach Material' folder (Appendix 1). These materials and are available to partners engaging in

⁴ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en

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external communication. They may be used as they are or may be downloaded as templates and tailored to the specific needs of the outreach activity.

Website/social media

The website for IMPULSE will be hosted on the EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC website.⁵ The website will contain details about the project consortium, workplan, communication resources and public deliverable reports. All further online information about IMPULSE (e.g., news, events, training calls, etc.) will be posted in the main EU-OPENSSCREEN feeds with an IMPULSE acknowledgement.

IMPULSE will also use the social media channels of EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC to communicate about project news and achievements. The primary channels will be LinkedIn (@EU-OPENSSCREEN) and X/Twitter (@EuOpenscreen). All IMPULSE-specific content will contain an acknowledgement of the project, including the project logo and the project-specific hashtag (#EUOSImpulse). Project partners communicating about IMPULSE via social media should also use this hashtag in all posts to boost project visibility.

2.6 Reporting

This section of the handbook provides guidelines for preparing and submitting reports to the EU, including the types of reports required, their frequency and the necessary content.

Periodic reporting

The Periodic Report and/or Final Report must be submitted through the EU Funding & Tenders Portal Grant Management System by the Coordinator within 60 days after the reporting period ends. This report is necessary to receive payments and includes both a technical and a financial report.

In IMPULSE, we will have two reporting periods (RPs):

- **RP 1:** from month 1 to month 18, duration 18 months (**01.03.2024–31.08.2025**).
- **RP 2:** from month 19 to month 36, duration 18 months (**01.09.2025–28.02.2027**).

These reports cover technical progress, financial expenditure and any deviations from the workplan. Detailed guidelines on how to prepare the periodic report are available online.⁶

All partners contribute to the periodic report. WP leaders are responsible for gathering information from their respective WP partners and ensuring that all data is accurate and submitted on time. The project coordinator is responsible for compiling the reports with input from project partners and WP leads and co-leads, verifying their accuracy and ensuring they meet the required standards before submission. All partners are expected to adhere to the reporting deadlines and provide the necessary documentation promptly.

Instructions on how to prepare the periodic report with tailored Word/Excel templates and timelines will be provided to project partners by the coordinator immediately at the beginning of each reporting period.

To streamline this process, the coordinator will use project management tools like Asana and EMDESK. These tools offer integrated task tracking and financial reporting features, which will facilitate the preparation of the report.

⁵ <https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/impulse-overview.html>

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/temp-form/report/periodic-report_horizon-euratom_en.pdf

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Continuous reporting

This section offers detailed guidance on the processes, tools and best practices for conducting continuous reporting throughout the project lifecycle. Reporting is carried out via the Funding & Tenders Portal.

Detailed guidelines on how to prepare the continuous reporting are available in the Funding & Tender Portal Online Manual.⁷

During the project, partners are required to provide regular updates on various aspects of the project, including:

- Progress in achieving milestones
- Completion of deliverables
- Updates to the publishable summary
- Responses to critical risks
- Publications, communication activities and intellectual property rights (IPRs)
- Programme-specific monitoring information (if applicable)

The project coordinator will regularly provide partners with tailored Word/Excel templates and timelines to facilitate this reporting process (Appendix 1). Updates are uploaded in the Continuous Reporting Module in Funding & Tender Portal.

Continuous reporting on communication, dissemination and exploitation

Project partners are expected to engage in outreach throughout the duration of the project to improve the visibility of the consortium and its achievements.

In accordance with continuous reporting requirements for the European Commission, all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities carried out by the consortium which acknowledge IMPULSE will be continuously monitored throughout the project. To facilitate this process, partners must enter all outreach-related activities into the 'Communication, dissemination and exploitation log' on SharePoint (Appendix 1). A description and example of these categories for continuous reporting is in Table 6.

Table 6 Requirements for communication, dissemination, and exploitation reporting.

Type of activity	Description	Examples
Communication	Activities which raise awareness about the project's objectives, activities, and impact.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Website updates ○ Newsletters ○ Social media posts ○ Blog posts ○ Success stories
Dissemination	<p>Activities which circulate knowledge, tools, and resources developed in the project.</p> <p>Aim is to make project outcomes available for use among the scientific community.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Publications ○ Conference talks/poster presentations ○ Workshops
Exploitation	Activities which concretely make use of the project's outcomes, often for commercial, societal, or policymaking purposes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Creation of new prototypes, software, technology, etc.

⁷ <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Online+Manual>,

<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/pages/viewpage.action?pagelId=1867968>

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It is the partners' responsibility to log all project-related communication, dissemination and exploitation activities in a timely fashion. These activities should ideally be logged on a rolling basis, but at latest every six months.

Continuous reporting on milestones & deliverables

Milestones and deliverables are submitted by each participant leading the deliverable/milestone to the coordinator and PMT. The coordinator will upload final deliverable reports and check milestones in the Continuous Reporting Module in Funding & Tender Portal according to the deliverable and milestone schedules.

See more details in the Review/submission process section.

Deliverables and milestones including their schedule are stored on SharePoint under 'Deliverables and milestones' folder (Appendix 1).

2.7 Quality management

Quality assurance

The IMPULSE coordinator and PMT are responsible for assessing and managing the quality of all materials produced within the project. Partners should be familiar with the guidelines below and adhere to them when producing documents for IMPULSE.

Document structure

Official documents produced for IMPULSE must include the following elements:

- Document title
- Version number and date created
- IMPULSE logo (stored on SharePoint; Appendix 1)
- European Union logo⁸
- Legal disclaimer:

Funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement No. 101132028. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Documents which contain proprietary information of the IMPULSE consortium must also include the following security disclaimer:

This document contains information which is proprietary to the IMPULSE consortium. Neither this document nor the information contained herein shall be used, duplicated or communicated by any means to any third party, in whole or in parts, except with prior written consent of the Coordinator. The information in this document is provided as is, and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at its sole risk and liability.

Language and naming conventions

All documents produced within the project must be written in British English.

All project documents stored on the IMPULSE SharePoint will use a common naming structure:

⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en

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YYMMDD_IMPULSE_WPXX (if applicable)_Document Short Name

Archiving

Finalised documents stored on SharePoint will be converted from their original format into PDF format within one month of completion. This practice, carried out by the Coordinator and IMPULSE PMT, ensures that documents which must be accessed at later timepoints in the project are not modified.

Each SharePoint folder will contain a subfolder entitled 'ARCHIVED'. Prior or outdated versions of documents, including the original modifiable files converted to PDF, are stored in this subfolder.

Working documents

All consortium partners are required to store their tasks and WP documentation in the designated folders specific to each WP (this does not refer to data produced within the project). This centralised approach ensures that all relevant information is easily accessible, well-organised and up-to-date, facilitating smooth collaboration and efficient project management across the consortium. Partners must ensure that all technical documentation is uploaded promptly and consistently to these dedicated folders to maintain the integrity and transparency of the project's progress.

Deliverables and milestones acceptance management

Document structure

Deliverable and milestone reports must include all elements listed under 'Document structure' in the 'Quality management' section as well as a completed table of report identifiers. This table, as well as all other required elements, is available in the deliverable report template on SharePoint (Appendix 1).

Updated/progressive versions need to contain a history of changes table.

Naming conventions

All IMPULSE deliverable and milestone reports use the following common naming structure:

YYMMDD_IMPULSE_Deliverable XX/Milestone XX_ Title_version

Review/submission process

Partners leading milestone(s) and deliverable(s) are responsible for the preparation of these activities in consultation with WP partners that contributed to the work described. WP leaders are responsible for ensuring that the content of the milestone(s) and deliverable(s) is correct and complete. WP leaders are in close contact with the WPLG and project coordinator and exchange information about the progress of the milestones and deliverable reports.

Finalised reports on milestones and deliverables should be submitted to the coordinator/WPLG at least two weeks before their deadline. Deliverables and milestones are reviewed by the WPLG and PMT before submission.

The coordinator will share the final reviewed reports with the general assembly members.

The project coordinator is responsible for submitting milestones and deliverables to the Granting Authority.

If there are any delays in delivering milestones or deliverables, they must be promptly reported to the coordinator, who will then inform the project officer.

SharePoint Archiving

The PDF version of each deliverable and milestone submitted in the Funding & Tenders Portal must be immediately uploaded to the 'Deliverables and Milestones' folder in SharePoint (Appendix 1).

The modifiable version of the deliverable/milestone must also be archived in SharePoint after submission (for details, see Archiving).

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After submission, the coordinator and PMT will update the deliverables and milestones registers on SharePoint accordingly, also available in the 'Deliverables and Milestones' folder.

Zenodo EU Open Research Repository

In addition to SharePoint, deliverable and milestone reports labelled 'PU' (public) in the IMPULSE Grant Agreement are archived on the Zenodo EU Open Research Repository.⁹ The IMPULSE PMT is responsible for uploading submitted public reports to this repository in a timely fashion after delivery.

2.8 Risk management

In IMPULSE, the PMT will ensure the proactive identification, assessment and mitigation of potential risks that could impact the project's objectives, timeline and resources. The PMT will establish a continuous risk management process, with regular monitoring and updates throughout the project's lifecycle. This process will include the development of a comprehensive risk register, where risks will be categorised by likelihood and impact, and appropriate mitigation strategies will be outlined.

All consortium partners are expected to contribute to risk identification and management, ensuring that any emerging risks are promptly addressed. The risk register will be discussed during monthly WPLG meetings to minimise disruptions and ensure that the project remains on track to achieve its goals.

The IMPULSE risk register is available on the IMPULSE SharePoint under Reporting > Project Continuous Reporting (Appendix 1).

2.9 Resources Management

The project coordinator is responsible for overseeing the proper use of resources across all WPs, ensuring alignment with the project's objectives and budget. We will employ specific tools, such as project management software (Asana) and financial tracking systems (EMDESK), to monitor resource allocation and usage in real-time. These tools will facilitate transparent communication among partners, provide insights into resource utilisation and enable timely adjustments to avoid over- or underspending. All partners are expected to manage their allocated resources diligently and report any issues or deviations promptly to the coordinator. By leveraging these tools, maintaining strict oversight and organising regular meetings with the PMT and WPLG, we aim to optimise resource use and ensure the project's smooth and successful execution.

3 Conclusions/Next step

In this deliverable report, we provide a clear set of guidelines for the IMPULSE consortium to help monitor of daily project activities and ensure smooth project progress. These guidelines are based on the IMPULSE Consortium Agreement, the Grant Agreement and the EU online manual. By adhering to the guidelines and best practices outlined here, all project partners can ensure effective collaboration, compliance with regulations and the successful achievement of our project goals. All project partners are encouraged to regularly consult this handbook and stay informed about any updates or changes.

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/impulse/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

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Table 7 History of changes

Date	Change(s) applied
30.08.2024	Version 1 established

4 Appendices

Appendix 1: Paths to IMPULSE SharePoint folders and documents

Name	Type of file SharePoint	Path
Contacts and mailing lists	Folder	IMPULSE Documents > Contacts and mailing lists
Legal Documents (e.g. consortium & grant agreements, formal notifications)	Folder	IMPULSE Documents > Legal Documents
WP 10 (Project Management)	Folder	IMPULSE Documents > WP > WP10_Management
IMPULSE branding guidelines	PDF	IMPULSE Documents > Communication_outreach > Branding > 240531 IMPULSE Visual Identity & Style Guidelines
Outreach Material	Folder	IMPULSE Documents > Communication_outreach > Outreach Material
Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation log	MS Excel file	IMPULSE Documents > Reporting > Project continuous reporting > IMPULSE_Dissemination_exploitation_report_LOG
IMPULSE logos	Folder	IMPULSE Documents > Communication_outreach > Branding > Logo
Deliverable report template	MS Word file	IMPULSE Documents > Template > IMPULSE Deliverable DX.X Title Template
Deliverables and milestones	Folder	IMPULSE Documents > Deliverables and milestones
Risk Register	MS Excel file	IMPULSE Documents > Reporting > Project continuous reporting > IMPULSE risk register
Continuous Reporting	Folder	IMPULSE Documents > Reporting > Project continuous reporting
Periodic Reporting	Folder	IMPULSE Documents > Reporting > Periodic reporting

Appendix 2: Useful external links

Name	Link
EU portal grant management service	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home
Funding & Tenders Portal Online Manual	https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Online+Manual
Communicating about your EU-funded project	https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en